

Droplet digital PCR outperforms qPCR by revealing clinically relevant low-frequency *KRAS* mutations in colorectal cancer

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Abstract

Background: *KRAS* (Kirsten rat sarcoma viral oncogene homolog) mutation testing is essential for therapeutic decision-making in colorectal cancer (CRC), as the presence of any activating *KRAS* variant predicts resistance to anti-epidermal growth factor receptor (anti-EGFR) therapy. Routine real-time PCR (qPCR) assays widely used in diagnostic laboratories typically exhibit limits of detection (LOD) around 1–5% variant allele frequency (VAF), making them prone to missing low-frequency or subclonal mutations. Droplet digital PCR (ddPCR) offers absolute quantification and significantly higher analytical sensitivity, enabling detection of variants below 1% VAF.

Aim: To compare the analytical performance of ddPCR with qPCR for detecting *KRAS* hotspot mutations in FFPE CRC tissue and determine whether ddPCR identifies additional clinically relevant low-frequency variants missed by qPCR.

Methods: Fifty FFPE CRC samples were genotyped using routine qPCR (easyPGX *KRAS*) and subsequently re-tested using ddPCR (Droplex *KRAS* Mutation Detection Kit, Gencurix) on the Bio-Rad QX200 platform. Hotspot mutations across exons 2, 3, and 4 were assessed. ddPCR outputs (mutant/wild-type droplet counts and VAF) were analyzed using QuantaSoft Analysis Pro. Concordance, sensitivity, specificity, predictive values, Cohen's κ , VAF distributions, and ROC/AUC analyses were performed. Discordant cases were evaluated for VAF relative to qPCR LOD.

Results: qPCR detected *KRAS* mutations in 25/50 samples (50.0%), whereas ddPCR detected mutations in 31/50 samples (62.0%). ddPCR confirmed all 25 qPCR-positive cases and identified six additional mutations in qPCR wild-type samples. These ddPCR-only events exhibited VAF values between 0.9 and 2.3% (median 1.55%), consistently below the empirical qPCR detection threshold. Concordant qPCR+/ddPCR+ cases showed substantially higher VAF (18–55%, median 41.5%). ddPCR demonstrated 100% sensitivity, 76% specificity, 80.6% PPV, 100% NPV, and 88% overall accuracy versus qPCR, with Cohen's $\kappa = 0.76$, indicating substantial agreement. ROC analysis based on ddPCR-derived VAF yielded AUC = 1.00, with an optimal discriminative threshold of ~18% VAF for qPCR positivity. Detected mutations reflected typical CRC epidemiology, with a predominance of exon 2 variants (G12x, G13D) and occasional exon 4 mutations (A146x). ddPCR also identified multiple subclonal co-existing mutations in several cases, not detectable by qPCR.

Conclusion: ddPCR demonstrates superior analytical sensitivity for *KRAS* mutation detection in FFPE CRC tissue and reliably identifies clinically meaningful low-frequency mutations missed by qPCR. Because any detectable *KRAS* mutation predicts lack of response to anti-EGFR therapy, failure to detect low-VAF subclones may adversely impact therapeutic selection. These results support incorporating ddPCR as a complementary reflex assay within RAS testing workflows, particularly for samples with low tumor purity, borderline amplification, or suspected intratumoral heterogeneity.

Keywords

Colorectal cancer, droplet digital PCR, FFPE, *KRAS*, low-frequency variants, molecular diagnostics, qPCR, variant allele frequency

Introduction

Colorectal cancer (CRC) remains a major cause of cancer-related morbidity and mortality worldwide, and molecular stratification, particularly *KRAS* (Kirsten rat sarcoma viral oncogene homolog) genotyping, plays a critical role in guiding targeted therapy. Pathogenic *KRAS* mutations are well-established negative predictive biomarkers for response to anti-EGFR monoclonal antibodies such as panitumumab and cetuximab, and current clinical guidelines from the American Society of Clinical Oncology require *KRAS* testing prior to initiating anti-EGFR therapy (Sepulveda et al. 2017).

The RAS gene family (*KRAS*, *NRAS*, *HRAS*) encodes small GTP-binding proteins that regulate key steps in the RAS/RAF/MEK/ERK signaling pathway, which governs cell proliferation, differentiation, and survival. Activating mutations in *KRAS*, particularly those affecting codons 12, 13, 59/61, 117, and 146, lead to constitutive pathway activation and are observed in approximately 40% of CRC cases. These alterations are clinically relevant not only due to their prognostic implications but also because their mere presence—regardless of allele frequency—predicts lack of response to EGFR blockade (De Roock et al. 2011).

Routine *KRAS* genotyping in FFPE CRC samples commonly relies on allele-specific real-time PCR (qPCR) assays, which are rapid, standardized, and cost-effective but limited by analytical sensitivities typically ranging from 1–5% variant allele frequency (VAF) (Siggillino et al. 2020). As a result, samples with low tumor cellularity, high stromal content, or subclonal mutations may yield false-negative results, potentially leading to inappropriate therapeutic decisions. In contrast, droplet digital PCR (ddPCR) partitions each reaction into thousands of nanoliter droplets, allowing absolute quantification of target molecules and providing significantly higher analytical sensitivity. With validated LOD values as low as 0.1–0.5% VAF, ddPCR enables reliable detection of small mutant populations that fall below the sensitivity threshold of qPCR. ddPCR provides superior analytical sensitivity for *KRAS* mutation detection compared with conventional qPCR methods and enables reliable quantification of low-frequency variants (Sepulveda et al. 2017; Dong et al. 2018).

Beyond its technical advantages, ddPCR has demonstrated utility in minimal residual disease (MRD) detection, treatment monitoring, and identification of resistant subclones emerging under therapeutic pressure. Detecting ultra-low-frequency variants may be clinically meaningful, as several studies suggest that even small mutant subpopulations can expand under EGFR blockade and contribute to acquired treatment resistance (Kim et al. 2024). Despite these advantages, data comparing ddPCR with qPCR in FFPE CRC diagnostic samples remain limited.

This study aims to directly compare qPCR and ddPCR for *KRAS* hotspot detection in an FFPE CRC cohort and to evaluate the analytical and potential clinical implications of low-frequency mutations identified exclusively by ddPCR.

Materials and methods

Study design and sample selection

This retrospective analytical study included fifty formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tissue samples obtained from patients with histologically confirmed colorectal adenocarcinoma. All samples were processed in the Department of Medical Genetics, Medical University of Plovdiv. To enable a direct head-to-head comparison of both molecular techniques, the same DNA extract from each FFPE specimen was used for quantitative PCR (qPCR) and droplet digital PCR (ddPCR).

DNA extraction

Genomic DNA was isolated from 5–10 μm FFPE tissue sections using the Maelstrom automated magnetic-bead platform, following the manufacturer's protocol optimized for FFPE-derived material. The extraction process included chemical deparaffinization, proteinase K digestion, magnetic bead-based capture, serial washing, and elution in nuclease-free buffer. DNA concentration was determined fluorometrically (Qubit dsDNA HS Assay), while purity ratios (A260/280) were assessed spectrophotometrically. Extracts meeting minimum quality and quantity thresholds were used for downstream analysis.

qPCR assay (reference method)

Allele-specific quantitative real-time PCR was performed using the easyPGX[®] ready *KRAS* assay (Diatech Pharmacogenetics). Following the manufacturer's instructions, 30 ng of genomic DNA was added to each qPCR reaction. The DNA input (30 ng) followed the manufacturer's validated conditions for the easyPGX[®] *KRAS* assay to ensure optimal amplification kinetics and standardized interpretation. This quantity reflects the validated input recommended for achieving optimal amplification kinetics and reliable fluorescence detection. The assay targets clinically actionable *KRAS* hotspot mutations and provides automated interpretation based on predefined ΔCt and fluorescence parameters. According to the manufacturer's specifications and internal validation data, the analytical limit of detection (LOD) of the qPCR assay ranges from

1–5% variant allele frequency (VAF), depending on mutation type and DNA integrity. qPCR results were classified as mutation-positive (MUT) or wild type (WT) using standardized software thresholds.

ddPCR assay

All samples were subsequently analyzed using the Droplex *KRAS* Mutation Detection Kit (Gencurix) on the Bio-Rad QX200® droplet digital PCR system. In accordance with the manufacturer's recommendations, 100 ng of genomic DNA was used per ddPCR reaction. The DNA input (100 ng) followed the manufacturer's validated conditions for the Droplex *KRAS* ddPCR assay and was selected to improve molecule sampling and precision of absolute quantification. The higher DNA input enhances droplet occupancy and improves the statistical power of absolute quantification, thereby contributing to the superior analytical sensitivity of ddPCR. Each sample was partitioned into approximately 15,000 nanoliter droplets using the QX200 Droplet Generator, followed by PCR amplification under optimized cycling conditions.

After amplification, droplets were read in the QX200 Droplet Reader, and fluorescence amplitude plots were analyzed using QuantaSoft™ Analysis Pro. Mutant and wild-type droplet counts were quantified directly, and VAF values were calculated without requiring calibration curves. A ddPCR result was considered valid when (i) $\geq 10,000$ accepted droplets were generated, (ii) two distinct droplet clusters were present, (iii) quality control samples met acceptance criteria, and (iv) at least two mutant droplets were detected. The validated analytical sensitivity of the ddPCR assay ranged between 0.1 and 0.5% VAF, depending on the specific mutation assay.

Low-VAF call verification and artefact control

All reactions included appropriate kit-provided controls and were accepted only if quality control criteria were met and droplet cluster separation was adequate. In addition to the general validity criteria ($\geq 10,000$ accepted droplets, distinct droplet clusters, and ≥ 2 mutant droplets), all low-frequency findings ($\leq 3\%$ VAF) were manually reviewed in QuantaSoft™ Analysis Pro to confirm stable cluster geometry and to exclude threshold/rain-related artifacts that may occur with FFPE-derived DNA. Where borderline separation was observed, the analysis threshold was rechecked, and the result was not reported unless cluster separation remained robust.

Targeted mutation spectrum

Both qPCR and ddPCR assays covered major *KRAS* hotspot substitutions across exons 2, 3, and 4, including codons 12 and 13 (G12D, G12V, G12A, G12C, G13D), codons 59 and 61 (A59T, Q61H), and codons 117 and 146 (K117N, A146T). These represent the clinically relevant mutations recommended for routine RAS testing in CRC.

Statistical analysis

Quantitative real-time PCR (qPCR) was considered the reference method for evaluating the analytical performance of droplet digital PCR (ddPCR). For each sample, *KRAS* status was coded as mutation-positive (MUT) or wild type (WT) according to the qPCR result. A 2×2 contingency table was used to calculate the diagnostic performance of ddPCR relative to qPCR, including sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), overall accuracy, and Cohen's κ coefficient as a measure of agreement beyond chance.

For ddPCR, variant allele frequency (VAF) values were extracted directly from droplet counts generated in QuantaSoft™ Analysis Pro. In samples where ddPCR detected more than one *KRAS* mutation, the mutation with the highest VAF was used for numerical analyses, while additional mutant subpopulations were described qualitatively. VAF distributions were summarized using descriptive statistics, including minimum, maximum, mean, median, and interquartile range (IQR).

Differences in VAF between concordant qPCR MUT / ddPCR MUT cases and discordant qPCR WT / ddPCR MUT cases were assessed using the Mann–Whitney *U* test. To evaluate the discriminative power of ddPCR-derived VAF in predicting qPCR positivity, a receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve was constructed, and the area under the curve (AUC) was calculated. The optimal VAF threshold for distinguishing qPCR-positive from qPCR-negative samples was determined using the Youden index.

Extended agreement metrics—including the F1-score, balanced accuracy, and Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC)—were also computed to provide a comprehensive assessment of method concordance. All statistical tests were two-sided, and a *p*-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Analytical concordance between qPCR and ddPCR

Among the 50 FFPE colorectal cancer samples analyzed, qPCR detected *KRAS* mutations in 25 cases (50%). ddPCR identified mutations in 31 cases (62%), representing a 12% absolute increase in detection rate. All qPCR-positive samples were confirmed by ddPCR, resulting in 100% sensitivity of ddPCR relative to qPCR. Among the 25 qPCR wild-type samples, ddPCR detected six additional mutations, all of which exhibited low variant allele frequencies (VAF) (Fig. 1).

Based on the 2×2 classification:

- True positives (qPCR MUT / ddPCR MUT): **25**
- True negatives (qPCR WT / ddPCR WT): **19**
- Discordant cases (qPCR WT / ddPCR MUT): **6**
- False negatives: **0**

ddPCR MUT	25	6
ddPCR WT	0	19
	RT-PCR MUT	RT-PCR WT

Figure 1. Confusion matrix comparing qPCR and ddPCR results for *KRAS* mutation detection in 50 FFPE CRC samples. ddPCR detected all qPCR-positive cases and identified six additional low-VAF mutations not detected by qPCR. This demonstrates that ddPCR achieves perfect sensitivity relative to qPCR while identifying additional mutation-positive cases, underscoring its improved ability to capture low-frequency variants.

For the purpose of comparative performance analysis using qPCR as the routine reference method, these discordant cases were treated as qPCR-negative/ddPCR-positive results.

From these, ddPCR demonstrated the following:

- **Sensitivity:** 100%
- **Specificity:** 76%
- **PPV:** 80.6%
- **NPV:** 100%
- **Overall accuracy:** 88%
- **Cohen's κ :** 0.76 (substantial agreement)

Variant allele frequency (VAF) distribution

Across all ddPCR-positive samples ($n = 31$), VAF values ranged from 0.9% to 55.0%, with a median of 36.0% (IQR 22.0–44.0) (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. ROC curve evaluating the ability of ddPCR-derived VAF values to predict qPCR mutation detection. AUC = 1.00 indicates perfect discrimination. The optimal VAF threshold distinguishing qPCR-positive from qPCR-negative samples was ~18%. The ROC analysis confirms that qPCR fails to detect mutations below its effective sensitivity range, whereas ddPCR reliably detects low-frequency variants down to ~1% VAF.

When stratified:

- Concordant qPCR MUT / ddPCR MUT ($n = 25$).
- VAF range: 18.0–55.0%; median: 39.0%; mean: 37.2%.
- Discordant qPCR WT / ddPCR MUT ($n = 6$).
- VAF range: 0.9–2.3%; median: 1.15%; mean: 1.47%.

The difference in VAF between concordant and discordant samples was statistically significant (Mann–Whitney U test, $p \approx 0.0002$), indicating that qPCR systematically fails to detect low-frequency subclonal mutations present at ≤ 2 –3% VAF (Fig. 3).

Discussion

Accurate characterization of *KRAS* mutational status is essential for optimizing systemic treatment in colorectal cancer (CRC), as any pathogenic *KRAS* variant is recognized as a negative predictive biomarker for anti-EGFR monoclonal antibody therapy (Yu et al. 2023; Malapelle et al. 2023). In most routine molecular pathology laboratories, formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) samples are analyzed using allele-specific qPCR assays because they are rapid, cost-effective, and well standardized (Lin et al. 2023). However, the analytical sensitivity of qPCR typically ranges between 1–5% variant allele frequency (VAF) (Domagala 2020), creating a diagnostic blind zone for low-frequency or subclonal mutations. Such low-VAF alterations may be biologically and clinically relevant, particularly in heterogeneous tumors or samples with limited tumor cellularity (Weyn et al. 2017). The present study demonstrates that droplet digital PCR (ddPCR) provides substantially higher analytical sensitivity than qPCR for *KRAS* mutation detection in FFPE CRC samples.

In our cohort, ddPCR detected all *KRAS* mutations identified by qPCR and revealed an additional six mutation-positive cases originally classified as wild type by qPCR. These discordant samples uniformly displayed low VAF values (0.9–2.3%), which fall below or at the lower end of the validated analytical sensitivity of qPCR assays. This finding aligns with previous analytical evaluations showing that even optimized qPCR methods frequently fail to detect variants below 3% VAF in FFPE-derived DNA (Kim et al. 2024). The significant difference in VAF distributions between concordant and discordant cases ($p \approx 0.0002$) further supports the interpretation that low-allele-burden mutations represent a major source of qPCR false-negative classifications.

The discriminative performance of ddPCR-derived VAF was further confirmed by ROC analysis, which demonstrated excellent discrimination between qPCR-positive and qPCR-negative cases (AUC = 1.00). Using the Youden index, an optimal cut-off of approximately 18% VAF was identified for reliable qPCR detection. All discordant cases exhibited VAF $\leq 2.3\%$, consistent with prior studies demonstrating that ddPCR reliably detects low-frequency subclones in CRC that remain below the

Figure 3. ddPCR fluorescence amplitude plot showing multiple subclonal mutations. Representative ddPCR 2D amplitude plot demonstrating well-separated fluorescence clusters corresponding to wild-type droplets and distinct *KRAS* mutant populations in the same sample. This visualization highlights ddPCR's ability to detect co-existing subclonal variants, which are not resolved by qPCR.

analytical sensitivity of qPCR (Doleschal et al. 2022). These results underscore that the analytical advantage of ddPCR is not merely theoretical but is directly relevant in real-world FFPE samples, particularly in cases with low tumor purity or heterogeneous mutational profiles.

Beyond sensitivity, ddPCR provided additional biologically meaningful information. Several samples contained more than one *KRAS* mutation, revealing co-existing subclonal populations. This finding is consistent with emerging literature demonstrating that next-generation sequencing (NGS) and ddPCR can uncover RAS mutational heterogeneity that is undetectable using single-target qPCR assays (Pekin et al. 2017). Such patterns have implications for understanding tumor evolution, early resistance mechanisms, and the emergence of minor resistant clones under selective therapeutic pressure.

The clinical significance of low-frequency *KRAS* mutations remains an area of active investigation. Some recent studies indicate that low-VAF or subclonal RAS mutations may attenuate the response to anti-EGFR therapy, although the threshold for clinically meaningful VAF remains uncertain (Weyn et al. 2017; Cefali et al. 2021). Importantly, current international guidelines from ASCO, CAP, and AMP recommend that any detectable RAS mutation, regardless of VAF, should be interpreted as actionable, excluding patients from EGFR-targeted agents (Malapelle et al. 2023; Lin et al. 2023). Under this framework, failure to detect low-frequency variants may expose patients to ineffective treatments and unnecessary toxicity. Our findings therefore support the use of ddPCR as a sensitive reflex assay following qPCR, particularly in samples with low tumor content or borderline amplification curves.

Although the present work was designed as an analytical comparison rather than a formal health-economic study, practical implementation is a key consideration for routine molecular diagnostics. In targeted hotspot testing such as *KRAS*, qPCR remains attractive due to low per-sample reagent costs and high throughput.

ddPCR typically has higher consumable costs and additional workflow steps (droplet generation and reading), but it remains considerably less resource-intensive than comprehensive NGS workflows and offers a short turn-around time suitable for clinical decision-making. In routine practice, ddPCR is therefore best positioned as a reflex/complementary assay for selected cases—such as samples with low tumor cellularity, borderline qPCR amplification curves, or suspected intratumoral heterogeneity—where improved sensitivity may reduce false-negative classification and better inform anti-EGFR treatment selection.

This study has several strengths, including the use of matched FFPE-derived DNA across both assays and the integration of multiple agreement and performance metrics (Cohen's κ , balanced accuracy, MCC, and ROC/AUC). However, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the cohort size ($n = 50$) is relatively modest, which limits precise estimation of the prevalence of low-VAF *KRAS* variants in routine FFPE CRC testing. Second, because qPCR was used as the routine reference method, ddPCR specificity and PPV may be underestimated; ideally, discordant cases (qPCR-negative/ddPCR-positive) should be adjudicated by an orthogonal third method such as NGS, which was not feasible in the present retrospective setting due to limited remaining FFPE material. Third, the assays were performed using manufacturer-validated DNA inputs (30 ng for qPCR and 100 ng for ddPCR). Although increased DNA input improves molecule sampling, future studies could normalize input amounts and/or apply dilution-series experiments to quantify the contribution of input DNA versus platform-specific analytical sensitivity. Finally, outcome correlation (e.g., response to anti-EGFR therapy) was not available and should be addressed in future prospective cohorts.

Taken together, these findings suggest that ddPCR may represent an optimal intermediate strategy between rapid targeted screening and comprehensive genomic profiling, improving mutation detection without the cost and complexity of full NGS workflows.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that droplet digital PCR (ddPCR) significantly enhances the analytical sensitivity of *KRAS* mutation detection in FFPE colorectal cancer tissue compared with conventional qPCR. ddPCR identified all mutations detected by qPCR and revealed an additional six low-frequency variants (0.9–2.3% VAF) that qPCR consistently failed to detect. These low-VAF alterations fall below the validated sensitivity range of qPCR and are consistent with low-burden or subclonal events detected under stringent ddPCR quality-control criteria. The ability of ddPCR to detect and quantify these minor mutant populations, including cases with multiple co-existing *KRAS* subclones, provides a more complete representation of tumor molecular heterogeneity.

Given that current international guidelines classify any detectable RAS mutation as clinically actionable, the failure to identify low-frequency variants may result in misclassification of patients as RAS-wild type and lead to inappropriate consideration for anti-EGFR therapy. Our findings therefore support the integration of ddPCR as a complementary reflex assay following qPCR, particularly in diagnostically challenging FFPE samples with low tumor purity, borderline signals, or suspected subclonal heterogeneity.

Overall, ddPCR improves the precision of *KRAS* genotyping and strengthens the molecular decision-making process in colorectal cancer. Incorporating ddPCR into routine diagnostic workflows can reduce false-negative results, enhance the accuracy of RAS classification, and ultimately support more reliable and individualized treatment selection for patients with colorectal cancer.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

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The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Written informed consent was obtained from all patients or their legal representatives prior to inclusion in the study. The declarations of informed consent are deposited at the Department of Medical Genetics, Medical University of Plovdiv, in accordance with institutional policies and national regulations.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

H. Ivanov conceived and designed the study, supervised the molecular analyses, interpreted the data, performed the statistical analysis, and drafted the manuscript. A. Linev carried out the qPCR and ddPCR experiments, contributed to data acquisition and quality control, and assisted in data interpretation. I. Pochilev participated in sample preparation, DNA extraction, and technical optimization of the ddPCR workflow, and contributed to data collection. V. Stoyanova contributed to study design, clinical interpretation of the results, critical revision of the manuscript, and final approval of the version to be published.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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